

शिक्षक-शिक्षा शोध पत्रिका

(Shikshak-Shiksha Shodh Patrika)

(An International Journal of Teacher-Education)

Chief Editor :

Dr. Karunesh Kumar Tewari

23. Enumeration and conservation of Angiospermic flowering trees of Jabalpur (M.P.) Region with special emphasis on endangered species 97-106
Karuna S. Verma, Subhash Shah Dhurve, Aparna Awasthi and Lekhram Patel
24. Rethinking into Teacher Education : Need of the hour 107-113
Dr. Radha Dua, Pratibha Sagar
25. ICT in Teacher Education : Maximizing Pedagogical Effects 114-123
Shamim Ahmad, Mahendra Singh
26. A Study on Mental Abilities of Adolescents in Relation to Sex, Socio-Economic Status and Medium of Instructions 124-128
Smt. Sharmistha Das, Dr. Shyamrondar Bairagya
- Call for the Articles 129-129

Rethinking into Teacher Education : Need of the hour

Dr. Radha Dua¹, Pratibha Sagar²

1. Associate Prof. : (MJP Rohilkhand University)
2. Assistant Prof : (MJP Rohilkhand University)

“If you are a teacher in whatever capacity, you have special role to play. Because more than anybody else, you are shaping generations” Kalam & Ranjan 1998.

The progress of a nation depends upon the quality of its citizens which in turn is contingent upon its educational system. The teacher plays a crucial role in the nation building. They are the social engineers and custodians of the future. They have the capacity to mould the characters and minds of the future generation. In today's complex world with knowledge explosion, the role of teacher is not as simple as it was once. Besides, knowledge and skills, he has to promote understanding and tolerance among his pupils too. In a developing nation like India, teacher's role in national development is felt all the more. Various commissions have acknowledged the key role of teachers and emphasized on their quality education too.

The Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) remarked, “We are however convinced that the most important factor in the contemplated educational reconstruction is the teacher, his personal qualities, his educational qualifications, his professional training and the place that he occupies in the school as well as in the community”.

National Council of Teacher Education, NCTE (1998) has also stressed that only enlightened and emancipated teachers lead communities and nations in their march towards better and higher quality of life. The UNESCO report of the International Commission on Education (1996) also emphasized on the necessity of rethinking of teacher education for the human and intellectual qualities in the future teachers. In spite of many efforts to improve the quality of teacher education, no radical transformation has been observed as envisaged by NPE, 1992. To make India a

knowledge super power by 2020, it hardly needs stressing that the education of its teachers to be assigned a high priority. Today there is a great need of the teachers who can lead the future citizens towards a better tomorrow. Need of the hour is competent, efficient and responsible teachers who can lead the country on the path of progress. Hence great responsibility lies on the shoulder of training institutions for making our prospective teachers competent enough to lead the future generations.

Basic Qualities of A Would Be Teacher:

1. Mastery over the content and ability to communicate the same in an efficient way among his students.
2. Honest, punctual, sincere, dynamic, dedicated, devoted, committed. creative, hardworking and innovative in his attitude.
3. Mastery over the teaching skills and competent enough to handle and use appropriately modern techniques for class room instructions.
4. Skills of appropriate selection and use of variety of teaching methods.
5. Ability of handling of large heterogeneous classes and dealing with their difficulties whether these are content related or emotional/ adjustment related or any other.
6. Ability to help their students for their proper and continued all around development; cognitive, affective as well as psychomotor.
7. Ability to search talented and creative students.
8. Ability of shaping the behaviour of students in a desirable way to make them good citizens of the country.
9. Must be a Role model.
10. Counselor and as a guide to his students to plan their future courses / career in accordance with their abilities, interests, aptitudes, their economic status and the jobs prospects.
11. Ability to harmonize relations between the community and the school and also to cope with the social problem like illiteracy, poverty,

population explosion, environment pollution, health hazards communal harmony and any other current problems related with society.

In the backdrop of this discussion it comes to mind, do our prospective teachers possess the desired qualities in them to meet the challenges of the present day education / classroom? The general perception about the present teacher education programme is that only mediocre are coming to this profession. It is being felt that efficient, dedicated and committed teachers are not coming out of these institutions.

Drawbacks of the Present Day Teacher Education Programme and Some Suggestions

1. It is common experience that selection process for training of teachers is not upto the mark. Trainees usually selected are of mediocre stuff. They do not possess the desired attitude and aptitude for this profession. It is generally observed that the best lot of academically bright and intellectually superior goes to medical, engineering or other technical courses after 12th class. Some opt for graduation and higher studies and choose their career as scientists, business managers or administrators. The personality and the aptitude of the individuals opting for this profession is most important, hence it must be assessed properly before their entry into the teacher training programme. Hence entrance test for B.Ed trainees should give proper weightage to their aptitude, intelligence, reasoning, general awareness and knowledge of the subject matter. For those who pass the test, group discussions and interviews should also be made mandatory.

Besides academic intelligence, social intelligence and emotional intelligence and other related abilities must also be assessed. Today emotional intelligence is a key for survival in the fast paced society as it empowers an individual to know, understand and deal with one's own emotions and handle others in an effective way.

2. Practice teaching time period allotted in the present training programme is not adequate in terms of duration and experience to be gained (Ramamurthy Committee, 1990). Education Commission (1952-53)

also suggested that period of training programme should be of two academic years. Kothari Commission (1964-66) also emphasized that the duration of B.Ed. courses should be increased to two years. In most of the training institutions more emphasis is laid on theory in respect to marks. Mostly the training institutions do not have practicing schools of their own. The other schools where the practice teaching is arranged, give their school for a limited time period, hence B.ed. Trainees are not given ample time for practice in teaching. They are under pressure to complete their lesson plans anyhow. They do not master in the basic skills required for teaching in such a short period of time. Skill development of pupil teacher should be at par with their counterparts of abroad and this can be done only if proper emphasis is given to practice teaching and its duration is increased.

3. It is felt that the mastery in routine work of the actual school setting, when these prospective teachers will enter into profession i.e. preparation of time table, organization of school activities, co-curricular activities, maintenance of attendance register, discipline of the school or that of class, work related with the conduction of examination, paper setting, evaluation etc. can be given in the actual school setting only. Actual school experience, internship with practice of teaching can be introduced. Here the trainees can get actual training of the basic works of a teacher required during his career.
4. The B.Ed teacher trainees have to prepare the lesson plans according to the guidelines taught to them during their training but due to shortage of time period allotted for practice teaching, they are unable to follow them completely. Further, the lesson plans are checked superficially by the teacher educators. Moreover, the team of teacher educators fails to supervise all the lessons taught by the trainees thoroughly giving due time. The supervisor teachers also should have enough time to observe the student teacher's teaching.
5. Old teaching methods are used in teacher training institutions, the teacher educators themselves teach through lecture method only. They do not use the teaching aid or the content specific pedagogy in their

day to day classroom teaching. How can we expect a pupil teacher to use the modern method when he has not seen his teachers doing so? Hence if we want that our prospective teachers should use child centered approach, training for modern teaching methods and as well as of technologies must be given priority during the teacher development programme and the teacher educators themselves also use new technologies while delivering their lectures.

6. A suitable structural change in teacher education course is must.
- (i) Today's society is highly materialistic & persistent erosion of values is the high characters of the society. Man has become self centered. Universal values need to be included in teacher's training programme, it will filter down among the younger generation automatically. Team work and co-operation are the underlying principles of today's life progress and for lessening stress also.
 - (ii) Daily newspapers or TV news show that adolescents are committing suicides or are sometimes indulging in antisocial deviant behaviour also. Today's young generation is under tremendous pressure of their parents and the society and they want to prove themselves topper on every front or want to show themselves super. Hence when they do not show their best in the examination, this sometimes results into taking up extreme steps of ending of their life. (3 young adolescents committed suicide in Bombay, Times of India, 5th Jan, 2010). Within 23 days 20 persons have committed suicides (Hindustan Times, 5th Feb, 2010) Suicides in UP are also on increase. A majority of those who committed suicides are teenagers who are unable to bear the pressure of education. This issue of suicides has rocked U.P. Vidhan Sabha too (Hindustan Times, 5th Feb, 2010). It is felt that prospective teachers must be trained in guidance and counseling for helping their students and their parents to generate confidence among the students.
 - (iii) The bulging population of our country is the root cause of failure of all the developmental programmes of the country. Inculcation

of population education in the curriculum as a part of theory paper does not suffice the purpose. Teacher training institutions can come forward to sensitize the future teachers with gravity and management of this problem. These enlightened teachers will be good messengers for spreading the message of population control and family planning. They can bring the social change.

- (iv) Besides, the components of human rights and peace education, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence should also be incorporated in B.Ed curriculum to equip the prospective teachers with the ability to carry their function effectively and inculcate the sense of peace, human rights and responsibilities also among the would be teachers as responsible citizens of the tomorrow.
 - (v) For making prospective teachers computer friendly, compulsory component of computer education in the present system can be designed as in today's fast paced world knowledge of computer is must. Globalization has made the use of ICT in teaching learning process indispensable.
7. Privatization of teacher education has lead to opening of a number of private institutions of teacher education to accommodate the large number of B.Ed aspirants. The govt. and regulatory bodies should take stern action and must ensure the quality of teacher education. Unfortunately these new institutions instead of laying stress on quality are interested in making money.
 8. The infrastructure of teacher's training institutions particularly of those of govt. institutions should be taken care of, as good infrastructure ensures the quality of education. Secondary schools can be attached to the teachers training institutions as their laboratories.
 9. Continuous evaluations in teacher's training programme is the necessity of the day. It is observed that sometimes some B Ed trainees during their course time are involved in some other jobs. The continuous evaluation will improve on one hand the quality and on the other hand

it will ensure regularity of the pupil teachers and thus teach them lesson of discipline also.

In the light of above discussion there is urgent need to rethink into present day teacher education programme for equipping the Prospective teachers intelligently to face the challenges of the modern era as the school curriculum is changing; new areas of knowledge are being incorporated in. Also one time teachers training will not suffice, to make them update with the new areas of knowledge continuous in-service programme can be organized both through face to face and distance mode as well. Further in addition to train the prospective teachers for normal children, some specific training for the duration of one year can be designed to the desirous trainees for children with special needs (WSN) also.

STATEMENT ABOUT OWNERSHIP OF
शिक्षक-शिक्षा शोध पत्रिका
SHIKSHAK-SHIKSHA SHODH PATRIKA
(An International Journal of Teacher-Education)

1. Title : Shikshak shiksha Shodh Patrika
शिक्षक-शिक्षा शोध पत्रिका
2. Place of Publication : Faizabad, U.P., INDIA
3. Periodicity : Quarterly
4. Language : Bilingual (Hindi and English)
5. Owner's, Printer's,
Publisher's Name : Smt. Seema Tewari
6. Chief Editor Name : Dr. Karunesh Kumar Tewari
- Nationality : Indian
- Address : 231, KASHMIRI MUHALLA,
SAHABGANJ,
FAIZABAD, (U.P.) 224001 (INDIA)
- Mobile No. : 09336659850
- E-mail : karuneshkumartiwari@yahoo.com
: kkt231@yahoo.com

I, Smt. Seema Tewari hereby declare that the particulars given above are true to the best of my knowledge and belief.

(Smt. Seema Tewari)

Publisher.